

m.p. 122°. The identity of the compound was established by direct comparison with an authentic sample. Further elution of the column with petrol-EtOAc (2 : 1) furnished dengibsin (2a); 0.06 g), crystallised from MeOH-CHCl₃ (9 : 1), m.p. 227°. With Ac₂O/py it formed the diacetate (2b), crystallised from MeOH-CHCl₃ (9 : 1), m.p. 196°.

Chromatography of the neutral fraction as above afforded further amounts of ayapin (0.1 g) and aesculatin dimethyl ether (0.05 g).

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Extractive Spectrophotometric Method for the Determination of Iron in Titanium Base Alloys using 4-(2-Pyridylazo)resorcinol and a Long Chain Quaternary Ammonium Salt

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LITERATURE reveals several highly sensitive spectrophotometric methods for the determination of iron based on the complex formation of iron with 4-(2-pyridylazo)resorcinol (PAR)¹⁻⁶. However, as PAR forms complexes with many metal ions, the above procedures are less selective and find little application in the analysis of complex samples in the diversified matrix. In our investigations we have observed that iron(III)-PAR anionic complex can be quantitatively extracted using cetyl dimethyl benzyl ammonium cation as intensely red coloured ion-pair, in chloroform in the pH range 6-7.5. When EDTA is added after complex formation of iron(III) with PAR, the interference of many metal ions can be effectively suppressed without causing any error in the determination of iron which has been exploited as a selective spectrophotometric method for the determination of iron in titanium alloys.

Experimental

All the chemicals used are of AnalaR grade. Absorbance measurements were made with a Systronics 105 MK(II) spectrophotometer.

General extraction procedure: To an aliquot of the sample containing 1-40 μg ml⁻¹ of iron were added 1 × 10⁻³ M PAR (2 ml), 1 × 10⁻³ M EDTA (5 ml), 2 × 10⁻³ M CDBA (2 ml) and phosphate buffer (pH 6.7; 5 ml) solutions in sequence. The total volume was made up to 20 ml with

distilled water and then equilibrated with chloroform (20 ml) for 1 min. Two layers were allowed to separate and the red coloured organic extract was taken in 1 cm quartz cell and the absorbance was measured at 505 nm against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Iron(III)–PAR–CDBA system is best extracted in the pH range 6–7.5 into chloroform and the colour is stable for more than 20 h. A one-minute equilibration period is sufficient for quantitative extraction of the system. The overall concentrations of 1×10^{-4} M PAR and 2×10^{-4} M CDBA are found to yield best results for the estimation of 0–40 μ g of iron in 20 ml. Though small changes in the concentration of the reagent do not affect the absorbance, the use of very large excess of CDBA ($\geq 2 \times 10^{-3}$ M) should be avoided as it results difficulty in the separation of two phases.

The absorption spectra of iron(III)–PAR–CDBA show maximum absorbance at 505 nm and obeys Beer's law in the range 0–40 μ g/20 ml of iron(III) with a molar absorptivity 6.0×10^4 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The method is more sensitive ($\epsilon = 6.0 \times 10^4$) than those reported earlier for iron complexes with *o*-phenanthroline⁷ (1.1×10^4), bathophenanthroline⁸ (2.2×10^4), sulphosalicylic acid⁹ (2.6×10^3), 2,4,6-tri(2-pyridyl)-3-triazine (TPTZ)¹⁰ (2.2×10^4), xylene orange¹¹ (2.66×10^4) and PAR⁵ (5.6×10^4) in aqueous medium.

temperature within 2 min (PAR replaced by EDTA). However, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Pb^{II} interfere due to slow kinetic nature of these metal ions in the above replacement reaction.

Applications : The method was applied for the estimation of iron(III) in titanium base alloys. A sample of base alloy (NBS 176, NBS 50(a), 50(b), 50(c), 651) was dissolved in a mixture (120 ml) of H₂O–H₂SO₄–HCl (4 : 1 : 1). Then enough nitric acid was added to it to oxidise Ti^{III} to Ti^{IV} and colour of the solution changed from purple to colourless. For alloys containing tin, the solution was boiled for 5 min until it becomes bright yellow. Precipitate if formed was washed thoroughly with dilute HNO₃ (1 : 4) and the filtrate and washings were collected quantitatively. A 5M H₂SO₄ (10 ml) was added to the filtrate and evaporated until fumes of H₂SO₄ appear, then cooled and water (100 ml) added. The filtrate was then digested the solution became clear. To separate iron from titanium matrix, the filtrate was made up to 50 ml keeping the overall acidity at 5.5 M with HCl. Iron(III) was extracted quantitatively with diethyl ether (3 $\times$ 20 ml). The combined ether extracts was evaporated, the residue dissolved in 2M HCl (10 ml) and transferred to a 250 ml volumetric flask and made up to the mark. An aliquot of the above solution was taken and the amount of iron determined following the general extraction procedure. The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1 – DETERMINATION OF IRON IN TITANIUM BASE ALLOYS

Alloy (composition)	Sample taken mg	Iron found %	Relative error %	R.S.D.	S.D.
NBS No. 176. Titanium base alloy (Al, 5.16; Fe, 0.07; Mn, 0.0003; Sn, 2.47; C, 0.015; Cu, 0.003; Mo, 0.0003)	1000	0.075, 0.068, 0.072, 0.060	7.14, 2.86, 2.86, 1.43	3.370	0.004
NBS 50(a). Titanium base alloy (Fe, 0.19; Mn, 1.60; Al, 2.74)	500	0.192, 0.198, 0.188, 0.186	1.05, 4.21, 1.05, 2.11	2.104	0.005
NBS 50(b). Titanium base alloy (Fe, 0.25; Mn, 2.48; Al, 4.03)	600	0.245, 0.252, 0.256, 0.247	2.00, 0.80, 2.40, 1.20	1.600	0.005
NBS 50(c). Titanium base alloy (Fe, 0.25; Mn, 2.55; Al, 4.03; Ni, 0.018)	400	0.248, 0.254, 0.246, 0.251	0.80, 1.60, 1.60, 0.40	1.100	0.003
NBS No. 651. Titanium B unalloyed (Al, 0.006; Fe, 0.058; Sn, 0.026; Cr, 0.037; Si, 0.011; V, 0.021; Mo, 0.031; Mg, 0.001; W, 0.39; Cu, 0.038)	1000	0.053, 0.057, 0.055, 0.060	8.62, 1.72, 5.17, 3.45	5.308	0.003

Effect of interfering ions : A 1×10^{-3} M EDTA is tolerated when added after formation of iron(III)–PAR complex. Interference of foreign ions (concentration in parenthesis, μ g), such as Ag^I (50), Ti^{III} (100), Hg^{II} (500), Al^{III} (00), Bi^{III} (300), Cd^{II} (150), Cr^{III} (100), Cu^{II} (250), Mn^{II} (100), Sn^{II} (50), V^V (100), Zn^{II} (75), Mo^{VI} (150) and Pb^{II} (100) can be effectively masked if the extraction is carried out in presence of 5 ml of 1×10^{-3} M EDTA. As these foreign ions form labile complexes with PAR, they are decomposed completely by EDTA at room

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Trace Determination of Titanium by Differential Pulse Polarography

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VARIOUS polarographic techniques such as cathode ray polarography¹, a c. polarography², oscillopolarography³ and DPP^{4,5} have been reported for trace analysis of titanium(IV). Present work describes DPP procedure for trace determination of titanium(IV).

Experimental

The investigations were carried out on a Metrohm-E-506 Polarecord instrument. Electrodes employed were DME as working electrode, Ag/AgCl (satd. KCl) as reference electrode and Pt-metal as auxiliary electrode. The recording parameters maintained during the studies were as follows: initial potential, 0.0 V; potential range, -2.0 V; drop-time 1 s^{-1} ; paper speed, 60 mm min^{-1} ; scan rate, 8 mV s^{-1} ; and pulse amplitude, 16 mV. Total volume of the solution was 25 ml and deaeration was carried out by bubbling nitrogen for 15 min.

All chemicals used were of A R. grade. Stock solutions were prepared in double-distilled water and working solutions were prepared by suitable dilutions. Titanium solution (0. M) was prepared by dissolving TiO_2 in concentrated H_2SO_4 and volume made up with DDW.

Procedure: To a cell, 25 ml of solution containing EDTA (0.015 mol), KBrO_3 (0.004 mol) and NaOAc (0.1 mol) (pH 5.2) and 0.1% gelatin (25 μl) were added and a blank recording was made followed by addition of 75 μl of Ti^{IV} solution (3 ppm) and the polarogram was recorded.

A variety of electrolytes namely malonic acid, 5-sulphosalicylic acid, tartaric acid, citric acid, acetic acid, HCl, H_2SO_4 , HNO_3 , H_3PO_4 , HClO_4 , each at concentrations 0.01, 0.05, 0.1 and 0.2 M and a solution (I) containing EDTA (0.015 mol), KBrO_3 (0.004 mol) buffered with 0.1 M NaOAc and acetic acid at pH 4.8, 5.2, 5.6 and 6.0 were used for choice of base electrolyte.

Ti^{IV} exhibited well-defined peak in organic acids ($\geq 0.05 \text{ M}$) and solution (I). Solution (I) at pH 5.2 was selected as a supporting electrolyte as it showed high peak symmetry, good reproducibility and maximum peak current value.

Gelatin, triton-x-100 and bromophenol blue in the range 1×10^{-6} – $1 \times 10^{-3}\%$ were used as maximum suppressors. A $1 \times 10^{-4}\%$ gelatin solution was also used as it gave symmetric peak with evenly rising steps and improved baseline. Linear calibration plots were obtained in the range 1–10 ppm, 0.1–1 ppm, 10–100 ppb and 2–10 ppb of Ti^{IV} . The lowest determinable limit was found to be 2 ppb. The RMD, SD and CV values for 1 ppm and 2 ppb were 0.14%, 4.6, 0.18% and 1.6%, 0.05, 2.0% respectively. Thus the method is highly sensitive and precise. The method was found to be fairly selective except for Co^{II} , Sn^{IV} and Sb^{III} which interfered. Ni^{II} could be tolerated upto 1 : 50 ratio, Bi^{III} and As^{III} upto 1 : 20, Pb^{II} and W^{VI} upto 1 : 10, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} upto 1 : 5, and Cr^{III} and Cu^{II} upto 1 : 2 ratio.

Determination of Ti in corn and barley: A known weight of dried and powdered plant material was dry-ashed in a muffle furnace at $600 \pm 25^\circ$. The ash was dissolved in concentrated HNO_3 and the solution boiled to dryness. The residue was taken up in double-distilled water and volume was made upto 100 ml. In case of barley, the ash was boiled with dilute HCl for 5 min. Undissolved silica was filtered off and the volume made upto 100 ml. A 10 ml aliquot was used for analysis. The results are presented in Table I and Fig. 1 (curves a and b; B=blank).

TABLE I – TITANIUM CONTENT IN PLANT MATERIALS AND COAL

Sample	Ti mg/100 g sample	
	Calibration plot method	Standard addition method
Corn	0.0214	0.0214
Barley	0.0248	0.0274
Coal	5.0180	4.8700

Determination of Ti in coal: An accurately weighed sample of coal from Rawanwara (Madhya Pradesh) was processed as described for barley. Quantitation of titanium in above samples was made with calibration plot method and standard